

Materials for teaching culture :tv, internet ,pictures

Andijan region English philology,

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Abstract: This chapter is an attempt to explore how localization of ELT materials can serve as a useful tool to preserve the cultural identity of EFL learners. To this end, I first examine two dominant trends in materials development, namely globally-produced versus nationally-produced materials and address the advantages as well as disadvantages of each. I will then argue that one of the main disadvantages of using globally-produced textbooks is that they generally reflect Western culture and ideology. This will be followed by a discussion of culture and ideology and how they are generally defined, which then paves the way for an argument that locally-produced materials act as a weapon against cultural and ideological invasion of global ESL textbooks.

Key words: Culture, literature, TV, Internet, newspaper, cultural events, teaching culture.

In this era of information and technology explosion, peoples in the world come into contact with one another more often and more easily than ever before. The need for mastering a foreign or second language besides one's own seems to dramatically grow. More people are learning languages for their personal and professional needs. Although the field of language teaching has done an excellent job to increasingly better accommodate the needs of language learners, the field may have to do even more and better to address the various needs of language

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learners. Specifically, cultural aspects of the language being learned must be taught concurrently with the linguistic aspects, which have traditionally been emphasized. Teaching culture to foreign or second language students may not be a novel topic, as it has repeatedly been discussed by a whole host of authors such as Atkinson (1999), Blatchford (1986), Brown (1986), Brown (2007a), Brown and Eisterhold (2004), Brooks (1986), Damen (1987), Morgan and Cain (2000), Tang (1999), Tang (2006), Valdes (1986), to name but a few. However, after decades of development in language teaching, one might wonder if culture has increasingly become an important component in the language curriculum as well as in the training programs for language teachers. Likewise, it may not be clear if researchers and authors in language teaching are still interested in finding out effective methods to integrate culture in second and foreign language classrooms. To that end, this paper attempts to partially shed some light on this issue.

Before any discussion on the relationship between language and culture can be carried out, it is first necessary to discuss some common terms such as language, culture, enculturation, acculturation, culture awareness, cross-cultural awareness, cultural identity, culture bump, and culture shock. An understanding of these basic terms will enable one to realize the importance of culture in language learning and teaching. Main part Language and culture are flip sides of the same coin. When you have one, you necessarily have the other. As a language educator, you are already fully aware of this. After all, language is a verbal expression of culture. It conveys our experience as a people. This is why Mongolian contains a rich vocabulary surrounding animals and French is a go-to language for food. It is why in Japanese, refusing an offer sometimes requires about three lines (two of which may involve apologizing), when a simple English “No” might suffice in a similar

situation. The American writer Rita Mae Brown once said, “Language is the roadmap of a culture. It tells you where its people come from and where they are going”. Beyond vocabulary and grammar rules, somewhere in the world, there is a group of wonderful people who use the language you are teaching in the classroom. They use it to buy milk, to chat with friends, to comment on Facebook statuses, to make songs and movies with. Their culture so beautiful, it can make the pages of a language textbook spring to life. As teachers, we are always looking for ways to make our lessons interesting, right. We go to great lengths just to maintain student interest in our classes. Well, culture is a very powerful hook. It can heighten the interest and motivation of your students. In the prism of culture, language classes instantly become exciting and educational experiences. What are some advantages and disadvantages of teaching culture in the classroom? It may seem obvious to many second or foreign language teachers that culture needs to be taught, but teaching culture in the classroom may not be as easy as one might have thought. In some cases such as contexts where English is learned as a foreign language, the language classroom may be the only way where cultural contact occurs; therefore, the environment should be made as open as possible to meaningful cultural learning (Damen, 1987). Damen noticed that there are both advantages and disadvantages when taking the language classroom as a specialized context for language and culture learning. In terms of the disadvantages, Damen reasoned that the classroom is only an unreal situation as opposed to the real world outside the classroom, so the practice of intercultural communication and experiential culture learning projects is mere practice and simulation. However, Damen also mentioned that culture learning in the classroom might present unanticipated advantages, because the members of a language class may be

considered as forming a transient, ad hoc group including a teacher and students whose communal existence is limited in time and space. Damen (1987) posited that learning culture in the classroom provides two distinct advantages. 1. As an artificial community, the classroom draws a culturally protective wall around those within, bestowing less severe punishment for the commission of linguistic and cultural errors that could be met outside its walls. 2. The classroom community is managed, unreal, forgiving, and protective, but it is also an environment that provides unique opportunities for experimental intercultural communication. If administered well, this community may provide the first step on a long voyage of cultural discovery that will end in the world outside the classroom. Moreover, in a recent study in Taiwan Tsou (2005) found that giving cultural instruction to foreign language learners increased not only their language proficiency but also their motivation toward language learning.

Conclusion In short, English has become an international language with all that involves in terms of culture, language and teaching this requires serious rethinking of the links of English speaking non-English speaking countries. It requires recognition that largely, English has become denationalized. This means that teachers, at as local a level as possible, make decisions that are appropriate so that learners will be able to use English to tell others about they own culture.

References:

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